

Improved DSSC Based on the PC Structure of Biomimetic Butterfly Wings

基於仿生蝶翅 PC 結構改進的染料敏化太陽能電池

Project Proposals | 項目企劃書

2012 Teco Green Tech Contest
Dye-sensitized solar cell

能源危機
Energy Crisis

世界城市灯光 | World city Light

全球共識

Global consensus

Working principle
of DSSC
Photosynthesis

New Type Solar Cells | DSSC

新型太陽能電池 | DSSC

產品展望

Products Outlook

節能減排

Energy Saving

15%
Reduction in
Manufacturing
Waste water

1
Toxic chemicals
Phased out
Of production

6%
Energy consumption
Reduction
over 2 years

開拓創新

Developing & Innovation

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Chapter 1 Project Background

第一章 專案背景

1. Creative motivation

Energy is the primary issue in the development of the world economy. Currently, many countries regard the development of new energy as a response to the financial crisis and an important measure to accelerate the economic recovery. As an inexhaustible clean natural energy, solar energy is one of the most promising energy. At present, the most extensive research and application of solar cells is silicon solar cells. Due to high raw material costs, complex production process and limited improved efficiency, silicon cells' civilian subjected to technical restriction. Compared to silicon solar cells, dye-sensitized solar cells have a relatively inexpensive price and potentially high photoelectric conversion efficiency, what's more, can be made into flexible products and simply fabricated. Therefore, it's most likely to replace the traditional silicon solar cells and become the dominant of the photovoltaic industry in the near future.

This project was enlightened by the optical properties of nature butterfly wings's photonic crystal microcavity structure that it could reflect a certain band of light and present beautiful colors. And generic into photonic crystal band gap materials which can be used in the anode light reflection layer of the third generation solar cells to improve the photoelectric conversion efficiency, so that a wide range of civilian becomes possible.

2. Existing Technology

Corresponded to the structure of dye-sensitized solar cells, advanced research is focused on the following three aspects: synthesis of new dye molecules; preparation of nano-porous TiO₂ film, selection of electrolyte and redox agent, optimization of the photocathode, research and application of solid electrolyte. Our research group's work is aim to optimize the structure of photoanode, combined with the characteristics of TiO₂ high electron injection efficiency and ZnO high electron transfer rate, using electrophoretic deposition, screen printing and slurry spraying method to prepared ZnO/TiO₂ composite film. Add biomimetic butterfly wings photonic crystal to the photoanode can make it absorb fully sunlight, which can improve the cell's property and the photoelectric conversion efficiency.

Our group has applied for two patents during the research of DSSC, and through the patent first trial on January 4, 2012. One is the continuous operation of the gas-liquid interface jig magnetic separation controlled ring-shaped device (Patent No. 201110355808.8). The other is annular gas-liquid interface jig magnetic separation device (Patent No. 201110355807.3). These two patents are used in the core technology of solar cell reflection enhancing film—the preparation of photonic crystal. Early in the preparation of photonic crystals, we need to separate the different size Particles and then assemble it. The homogeneity of sepatating particle size is the key technology which affects the excellent performance of the photonic crystal. As a reflective layer, the photonic crystal can reflect the incident light and transform it into electricity, thereby further enhancing the photoelectric conversion efficiency of the DSSC.

一、創作動機

能源是世界經濟發展的首要問題，當前，許多國家都把發展新能源作為應對金融危機、加快經濟復蘇的重要舉措。作為一種“取之不盡、用之不竭”的潔淨天然新能源，太陽能毫無疑問成為最有希望的能源之一。目前研究和應用最廣泛的太陽能電池主要是矽系太陽能電池，但矽系太陽能電池因其原料成本高、生產工藝複雜、效率提高潛力有限，其民用化受到技術性限制。染料敏化太陽能電池相對於矽太陽能電池價格較低、製作工藝簡單、可製成柔性襯底產品、擁有潛在的高光電轉換效率，所以極有可能取代傳統矽系太陽能電池，在不久的將來成為光伏產業太陽能電池的主導產品。

本作品受自然界常見的蝶翅光子晶體微結構呈現五彩斑斕顏色現象的啟發，根據其原理仿製成光子晶體禁帶材料，將其反射一定波段光線的光學特性應用於染料敏化太陽能電池的光陽極反射層中，大大提高其光電轉化效率，使其廣泛民用成為可能。

二、現有技術

與 DSSC 結構相對應，對染料敏化太陽能電池的研究主要集中在以下三個方面：新型染料分子的合成；納米 TiO₂ 多孔薄膜的製備工藝及優化；電解質及氧化還原劑的選擇和優化；對陰極結構的優化設計；固體電解質的研究與應用等。本研究組主要是對光陽極結構進行優化，結合 TiO₂ 高電子注入效率和 ZnO 高電子傳輸速率的特性，利用電泳沉積、絲網印刷及漿料噴塗等方法製備出 ZnO/TiO₂ 複合膜光陽極。並在此光陽極上增添仿生蝶翅光子晶體，得以充分吸收太陽光，改善電池的性能，提高其光電轉換效率。

在研究 DSSC 過程中，本專案研究組申請了兩項專利技術，已於 2012 年 1 月 4 日通過專利初審。其一是可連續作業的氣液介面跳汰磁分選可控環形裝置（專利號：201110355808.8）；其二是環形氣液介面跳汰磁分選裝置（專利號：201110355807.3）。此二項專利技術用於染料敏化太陽能電池反射增強膜核心技术—光子晶體的製備過程。在光子晶體的製備前期，需要對不同粒徑的顆粒進行分選然後組裝。粒徑分選的均一性是影響光子晶體性能優良的關鍵技術，光子晶體作為反射層，使入射光進行最大幅度的吸收從而更多的轉化為電能，進一步提高染料敏化太陽能電池的光電轉化效率。

Chapter 1 Project Background

第一章 專案背景

3. Research Progress

(1) High performance of DSSC

In the early 1990s, Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSC) has just appeared, its photoelectric conversion efficiency reached 7.1%-7.9%, creating a new field of research and development of new type solar cells. After ten years of efforts, so far, the photoelectric conversion efficiency has reached more than 12%.

(2) Flexible dye-sensitized solar cells

Traditional DSSC's substrate is the glass coated with indium-tin oxide, which has many problems such as fragile, not portable, not flexible and higher prices. While flexible DSSC use the lightweight polymer film or metal foil as the substrate and has the bending characteristics. Then it facilitates the battery reel continuous manufacturing process, greatly expanding the application fields of the DSSC.

(3) Amplification of DSSC area and device integration

Due to the high cost-effective of the DSSC, in the late 1990s, people began to research the amplification of the DSSC area and integrated with the device. In 2001, Australia STA Company established the world's first and only demonstration roof with an area of 200 m² DSSC, and it concentrating conveys the brilliant prospects of industrialization in the future. The Dai Songyuan research group, which is belong to Institute of Plasma Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, has been committed to the research about a large area of DSSC, and maintain the operation so far. Their efforts laid a great foundation for the next industrial production.

The single DSSC's providing voltage is limited, so the open circuit voltage is generally no more than 0.9V. If Using DSSC supplies power to electrical equipment and even to the grid, it must be in series or parallel. Recently, the Institute of Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences develops a production method of series and parallel in one DSSC module within the same cell module. One module consists of four series cells pack, each battery pack contains three parallel cell elements. This design process is simple and high yield, integrating in one DSSC module in series and parallel and with high voltage and high current, which can meet the requirements of voltage and current for a wider range of devices with a single cell

(4) DSSC's industrialization and costs reducing

DSSC's industrialization is still on the way. Because of the less use of materials, laboratory preparation's relative prices are more expensive, about 12 RMB per watt. After the introduction of industrial technology and design pipeline, DSSC's costs will be reduced by about 10% to 10.8 RMB per watt. There is a great cost advantage relative to the general silicon solar cell whose price is 25RMB per watts. In addition, the instruments of DSSC are relatively simple and easy to manufacture. And its production process has no heavy metals, poisonous gas and other pollutants, which makes the environmental load is small.

三、研究進展

1. DSSC 的高性能化

上個世紀 90 年代初，染料敏化太陽能電池 DSSC(Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells)初露崢嶸，其光電轉換效率達 7.1%-7.9%，開創了新型太陽能電池研究和發展的全新領域。經過十多年的努力，到目前為止，現在的光電轉換效率已經超過 12%^[1]。

2. 柔性染料敏化太陽能電池

傳統的 DSSC 以鍍有氧化銻錫的玻璃為基底，存在著易碎、不輕便、價格高等問題。柔性基底的 DSSC 則以輕質的高分子膜或金屬箔為基底，具有可彎曲變形的特性，便於電池的卷軸式連續製造工藝，大大拓展了 DSSC 的應用範圍。

3. DSSC 的大面積化與器件集成

由於 DSSC 的性價比高，20 世紀 90 年代末，人們開始著手研究 DSSC 面積的放大與器件集成。2001 年，澳大利亞 STA 公司建立了世界上第一個也是唯一一個面積為 200 m² 的 DSSC 電池示範屋頂，集中體現未來工業化的前景。中國科學院等離子體物理研究所的戴松本研究組也一直致力於大面積電池的研究工作，並保持項目運行至今，為下一步的工業化生產奠定良好的基礎。

單塊 DSSC 提供的電壓是有限的，其開路電壓一般不超過 0.9V，如果用 DSSC 給電器設備供電甚至並網發電，就必須將 DSSC 和模組進行串聯或並聯。最近，中科院物理研究所在模組串並聯方面作了一些改進，發展了一種能夠在同一電池模組內同時實現串聯和並聯的 DSSC 模組的製作方法。[9]該模組包括 4 個串聯的電池組元，每個電池組元包含有 3 個並聯的電池單元。該設計工藝簡單，成品率高，能在一個 DSSC 模組內實現集成並同時具備高電壓和大電流，從而可以用單塊電池滿足更廣泛的器件對電壓電流要求。

4. DSSC 產業化與成本降低

DSSC 的產業化進程還在起步當中，實驗室製備由於所用原料較少所以相對價格較為昂貴，約為 12 元每瓦。但在產業化引進並設計流水線之後，DSSC 的製作成本會降低大約 10%，為 10.8 元每瓦，相對於一般矽太陽能電池價格 25 元每瓦左右具有很大成本優勢。此外，DSSC 所用儀器相對較為簡單，容易大規模生產，工藝簡單，無重金屬、有毒氣體等污染物，環境負荷小。

Chapter II System Structure

第二章 系統架構

The system of this project is mainly divided into three parts: components of DSSC, detection and control circuitry, energy storage and load system, as illustrated below, the DSSC components is the core part of this project.

Figure 1 | The blueprint of the system

1. Solar cells system

(1) Structure of cells

The structure of the common DSSC includes: photo anode, sensitizer dyes, electrolyte and photo cathode. This project adds photo anode reflective layer which is made of photonic crystal of biomimetic butterfly wings structure on the basis of the common DSSC. The following is the function describing of each part:

a. Photo Anode

Photo Anode is consist of transparent FTO glass, nano-porous TiO₂ film and dye composition. Its main function is to load the sensitizer and transfer electronic to the external circuit quickly and efficiently. It's the basis of supporting the operation of DSSC and its performance is directly related to the efficiency of the whole cell.

b. Dye-sensitizer

In this project we use N719 as the Dye-sensitizer. Its molecular structure is formula as shown below. Dye-sensitizer is the heart of the DSSC. It produces a flow of electrons through continuous absorption of light and then it drives the the operation of the whole cell.

c. Photonic crystal of biomimetic butterfly wings

The photonic crystal of biomimetic butterfly wings is between the titanium film and photo cathode. Because of its broadband photonic band gap, when we apply it to the photo anode reflective layer of DSSC, it can improve the photoelectric conversion efficiency of the cell by the incident light reflecting and absorbing several times by the ZnO/TiO₂ photo anode.

本專案的系統主要分為三大部分：DSSC 元件、檢測控制電路系統、儲能及負載系統，如下圖所示，其中 DSSC 元件為該專案的核心部分。

圖 1 | 系統設計圖

一、太陽能電池系統

(1) 電池結構

普通 DSSC 的結構主要由光陽極、染料敏化劑、氧化還原電解質、光陰極四個部份構成，本專案在普通 DSSC 的結構基礎上增添仿生蝶翅光子晶體作為光陽極反射層，下面介紹各部件的功能：

1. 光陽極

光陽極由透明 FTO 玻璃、多孔納米 TiO₂ 薄膜以及染料構成。其作用主要是負載敏化劑，並將光生電子快速有效地傳輸至外電路，是支撐 DSSC 運作的基礎，其性能的好壞直接關係到電池的效率。

2. 染料敏化劑

本專案中使用的染料敏化劑為 N719，其分子結構式如下圖。染料敏化劑是 DSSC 的心臟，通過不斷吸收光產生電子流，驅動著整個電池的運作。

3. 仿生蝶翅光子晶體

仿生蝶翅光子晶體處於二氧化鈦薄膜與光陰極之間，因其具有較寬頻隙的光子禁帶，應用於染料敏化太陽能電池的光陽極反射層中，使入射光在 TiO₂/ZnO 複合光陽與光子晶體之間極經過多次反射吸收，從而提高電池的光電轉換效率。

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d. Electrolyte

Electrolyte used in this project is liquid electrolyte— I^3^-/I^- redox couples. It mainly plays a role in renewing dyes and transporting holes has a great influence on the characteristics of Thermodynamics and Kinetics in cell system and the photovoltaic.

e. Photo Cathode

Photo cathode consists of FTO glass and activated carbon. Its function is to collect the electronic in the external circuit and be the catalyst to reduce the titanium dioxide material in the electrolyte.

(2) Working principle

The following is the working schematic of improved dye-sensitized solar cells based on the photonic crystal structure of biomimetic butterfly wings.

Figure 2 | The schematic of DSSC

Cell's description of the working principle

- ✧ Sunlight (hv) irradiate the cell and the energy which the ground state dye molecules (S) absorb sunlight is excited, the electronics in the dye molecules are stimulated and transport to excited state (S*);
- ✧ The excited state electronic injected into the TiO₂ conduction band quickly, at the same time, the incident light which is not absorbed stimulates dye molecules and produces electronic through reflecting several times in the surface of the photonic crystal.
- ✧ The electronics transfer rapidly in the TiO₂ film and enrich in the conductive tablet, then flow to the electrodes through the external circuits.
- ✧ The dye molecules which are in oxidized state (S*) and the electron donor (I⁻) which is in electrolyte solution (I⁻/I₃⁻) return to the ground state through the photonic crystal redox, and then the dye molecules regenerate.
- ✧ Close to the electrodes, electrolyte solution receives electronic and be reduce so that it can complete a loop.

4. 電解質

在本專案中使用的電解質是液體電解質— I^3^-/I^- 氧化還原電對，主要起再生染料和傳輸空穴作用，並對電池體系熱力學和動力學特性以及光電壓有很大影響。

5. 光陰極

光陰極由 FTO 導電玻璃及活性炭構成。它的作用是收集外電路的電子，並催化還原電解液中的氧化鈦物質。

(2) 工作原理

下圖為基於仿生蝶翅光子晶體結構改進的染料敏化太陽能電池工作原理圖：

電池工作原理描述：

- ✧ 太陽光 (hv) 照射到電池上，基態染料分子 (S) 吸收太陽光能量被激發，染料分子中的電子受激躍遷到激發態 (S*);
- ✧ 激發態的電子快速注入到 TiO₂ 導帶中，同時其他未被吸收的入射光經過光子晶體表面多次反射再次激發染料分子產生電子;
- ✧ 電子在 TiO₂ 膜中迅速傳輸，在導電幾片上富集，通過外電路流向對電極;
- ✧ 處於氧化態的染料分子 (S*) 與電解質 (I⁻/I₃⁻) 溶液中的電子供體 (I⁻) 穿過光子晶體發生氧化還原反應而回到基態，染料分子得以再生;
- ✧ 在對電極附近，電解質溶液得到電子而還原，從而完成一個迴圈。

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(3) Production process

a. Preparation of ZnO/TiO₂ composite photo anode

Firstly, Zn powder was used as the raw material and oxygen or air as the reaction gas to prepare ZnO whisker (T-ZnOw) by high temperature gas phase method. Secondly, use electrophoretic deposition, screen printing, spin coating, doctor coating method to prepare the ZnO film. Thirdly, treated at 500 °C in muffle, then parameters the surfactant and the amount of organic solvents into P25 TiO₂ powder, in which the TiO₂ slurry can be obtained. Fourthly deposit the TiO₂ films on the ZnO seed layer by screen printing. Finally, get ZnO/TiO₂ composite photo anode.

b. Preparation of photonic crystal

Use the quasi-gaseous state reaction method to synthesize submicron porous PS/Fe₃O₄ microspheres, and then use separation technology applied from the national invention patent. Through the control of external field, chemical additives and other auxiliary ways, the submicron monodisperse porous PS/Fe₃O₄ microspheres can be obtained. Next, apply particle assembly method to achieve the orderly assembly of monodisperse porous microspheres. Finally, drying and burning, the Fe₃O₄ opal photonic crystal with excellent performance and the band gap can be achieved.

c. Preparation of photon cathode

Cut FTO glass and wash it with cleaning agent, and then clean it with 10% NaOH solution by ultrasonic. Then boil it a period of time in the degreaser. Finally, activate it in 10% H₂SO₄ solution. After above steps, use pencil method to spread graphite or use candle burning method to cover a layer of carbon black in the surface of FTO, thus the photo-anode can be obtained.

d. Cell assembly

After completing photo anode, the photonic crystal and the photo cathode three parts, inject the electrolyte and then assemble the cell. Next, in the same battery module, parallel the cell strings. As shown below, the battery module concludes four series cell pack with each battery pack containing three parallel cell units in order to get high output voltage.

(3) 生產工藝

1. ZnO/TiO₂ 複合光陽極的製備

首先利用高溫催化法以 Zn 粉為原料，以氧氣或空氣為反應氣體，高溫氣相製備得到氧化鋅晶須 (T-ZnOw)。再採用電泳沉積、絲網印刷、旋塗、刮塗等方法製備 ZnO 薄膜，置於馬弗爐中 500 °C 下熱處理之後得到 ZnO 種子層。接著在 P25 TiO₂ 粉體中參入表面活性劑和適量有機溶劑研磨製備 TiO₂ 漿料，然後經絲網印刷、噴塗、刮塗等方法在 ZnO 種子層上沉積 TiO₂ 薄膜，得到 ZnO/TiO₂ 複合膜光陽極。

2. 光子晶體的製備

使用准氣相反應法合成出亞微米級多孔 PS/Fe₃O₄ 微球，利用申請的國家發明專利的分選技術經外場控制、化學添加劑等輔助精細分選後，得到亞微米級、單分散的多孔 PS/Fe₃O₄ 微球；再採用顆粒組裝法，實現單分散多孔微球的有序化組裝，然後經過乾燥和煅燒，製備出帶隙性能優異的 Fe₃O₄ opal 光子晶體。

3. 光陰極的製備

將切割好的 FTO 導電玻璃先用清洗劑洗滌，再用 10% 的 NaOH 溶液超聲波清洗，然後在除油劑中煮沸一段時間，最後放入 10% H₂SO₄ 溶液中進行活化，經過以上處理後，利用鉛筆法在 FTO 上塗上一層石墨或利用蠟燭燃燒法覆上一層炭黑，得到光陰極。

4. 電池組裝

完成光陽極、光子晶體、光陰極主要三部分後，注入電解質進行單電池的組裝。組裝完成後，在同一電池模組內，進行電池的串並聯，如下圖，該電池模組包擴 4 個串聯的電池組元，每個電池組元包含有 3 個並聯的電池單元，以期獲得高輸出電壓。

Figure 3 | Production flow chart

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(4) Battery evaluation

a. Evaluation on battery performance

IV curve test: Use the solar cell IV characteristics to test the efficiency of the cell. From the IV curve we can get the main indicators of the solar cell performance, such as the short circuit current I_{sc} , the open circuit voltage V_{oc} , the fill factor FF and the photo-electro transition rate η_{global} etc..

Open circuit voltage: When the circuit is open (as the external resistance is infinite), the photovoltage is called the open circuit photovoltage.

Short-circuit photocurrent density: When the circuit is short-circuit (as the external resistance is zero), the photocurrent is called short-circuit photocurrent, and per unit area of short-circuit photocurrent is called short-circuit photocurrent density. The DSSC short-circuit photocurrent density is correspond to the visible part of the integration area in the photocurrent action spectra of IPCE. The larger the integration area is, the greater the short-circuit photocurrent density will be.

Filling factor: When the battery possesses a maximum output power, the current density J_{opt} multiply photovoltage V_{opt} and then divide both short-circuit photocurrent density and open circuit voltage.

$$FF = J_{opt} * V_{opt} / (I_{sc} * V_{oc})$$

Photoelectric conversion efficiency: The maximum output power of the battery P_{opt} divided by the input optical power P_{in} is called the photo-electro transition rate. $\eta = P_{opt}/P_{in} = I_{sc} * V_{oc} * FF / P_{in}$

I_{sc} and V_{oc} are the two most important parameters of battery, the larger value of I_{sc} and V_{oc} are the basis of higher photo-electro transition rate.

According to research by the Chinese Academy of Sciences in DSSC series, the battery performance of this project after measuring is as follows:

Figure 4 | The I-V curve of cells

(4) 電池評價

1. 電池性能評價

I-V 曲線測試: 利用太陽能電池 I-V 特性測試系統測試電池的效率，從 I-V 曲線圖中可以得到太陽能電池性能的主要指標，如短路電流 I_{sc} 、開路電壓 V_{oc} 、填充因數 FF 和光電轉換率 η_{global} 等參數。

開路電壓: 電路處於開路（即外電阻為無窮大）時的光電壓稱為開路光電壓。

短路光電流密度: 電路處於短路（即外電阻為零）時產生的光電流稱為短路光電流；單位面積短路光電流稱為短路光電流密度。染料敏化太陽能電池的短路光電流密度對應於光電流作用譜中 IPCE 在可見光部分的積分面積。積分面積越大，則短路光電流密度越大。

填充因數: 電池具有最大輸出功率時的電流密度 J_{opt} 和光電壓 V_{opt} 的乘積與短路光電流密度和開路電壓乘積的比值。即： $FF = J_{opt} * V_{opt} / I_{sc} * V_{oc}$

光電轉換效率: 電池的最大輸出功率 P_{opt} 與輸入光功率 P_{in} 的比值稱為光電轉換效率。即

$$\eta = P_{opt} / P_{in} = I_{sc} * V_{oc} * FF / P_{in}$$

I_{sc} 和 V_{oc} 是電池最重要的兩個參數，較大的 I_{sc} 和 V_{oc} 值是產生較高能量轉化效率的基礎。

本專案根據中科院物理所研究的 DSSC 串聯方式，測出串聯之後的電池性能結果如下：

圖 4 | 電池的 I-V 曲線圖

b. Battery Life Cycle Assessment

FTO、TiO₂、C、Ru etc.

2. 電池生命週期評價 (LCA)

Figure 5

導電玻璃、二氧化鈦、碳、鈦等

Chapter II System Structure

第二章 系統架構

2. Circuitry control system

(1) Hardware circuit design

P-channel MOFFET MOFFETRF4905 is selected as switch tube for the circuit. The tube possesses the advantages such as, small resistance, fast switching speed, excellent switching performance and high reliability etc.

D4 is the indicator light. It turns on when the charge is connected and off when the charge is disconnected. D2 and D3 are the Schottky Diode. Its forward voltage is 0.3V, the maximum conduction current is 20A. D3 is used to prevent anti-charge. When the battery voltage is greater than the solar cells, it can prevent the fromer from reverse charging to the later. D2 is the regulator. The microcontroller model of the system is PIC24FJ64GA006, and the A/D converter of 10 has a higher accuracy. We set the reference voltage of this system 0-5V.

(2) Working principle of circuit

The charge controller designed by our team uses the pic microcontroller to automatically control the solar panel charging the battery. Charging has two phases: fast filling and slow filling. Our battery voltage ranges from 2.75V to 4.20V. When the detected battery voltage is less than 3.70 V, the PWM output duty cycle is 100%, it was fast charging. When the detected battery voltage is between 3.70V and 4.20 V, the PWM output pulse of voltage resize according to the duty cycle, and it gets into the slow charging filling stage. When the detected battery voltage is higher than 4.20V, the PWM output pulse duty cycle is 0 and the charging stops.

(3) Specific workflow

Connect Solar panels to the left side of the circuit, the charging battery to the right. When the system begins to work, the microcontroller A/D module samples the battery voltage. When the sampled voltage is less than 3.70V, the duty cycle of the PWM module will be controlled to output 100% of the pulse. This stage is called the fast charge stage. When the output voltage is between 3.70V and 4.20V, according to the voltage magnitude (like battery power), the PWM will be adjusted to output. This stage is called the slow charge stage. When the voltage is above 4.20V, the PWM module will be controlled to output 0, then the charging stops. When the output pulse of PWM is high, the MOS can be conducted, and the base of transistor Q2 output large voltage by MOS transistor source, so Q2 also turns on. Due to D2, the switch voltage is -10V, the switch charges and the solar cell charges to battery. When the pulse is low, MOS tube and transistor Q3 cut off, the switch is disconnected and the charge stops.

二、控制電路系統

(1) 硬體電路設計

該電路選用的開關管為 P 溝道 MOFFET 管 MOFFETRF4905, 該管具有導通電阻小, 開關速度快, 開關性能好, 可靠性高等優點。

D4 為指示燈, 當充電進行時指示燈亮, 充電斷開時指示燈滅。D2 和 D3 為肖特基二極體, 正嚮導通電壓 0.3V, 最大導通電流 20A。D3 作用為防止反充, 當蓄電池的電壓大於太陽能電池時可以防止其向太陽能電池反充電。D2 起到穩壓作用。該系統所用的單片機型號為 PIC24FJ64GA006, 該單片機 A/D 轉換器為 10 位, 精度較高, 該系統的參考電壓我們設為 0~5V。

(2) 電路工作原理

小組所設計的充電控制器是使用 pic 單片機來自動控制太陽能電池板給蓄電池充電, 充電分為快充和慢充兩個階段。我們蓄電池的電壓範圍為 2.75V~4.20V, 當檢測到蓄電池的電壓小於 3.70V 即較低電量時, PWM 輸出占空比為 100%的脈衝進行快速充電; 當檢測到蓄電池的電壓介於 3.70V~ 4.20V 時, 根據電壓大小調整 PWM 輸出脈衝的占空比, 充電進入慢充階段。當檢測到蓄電池的電壓大於 4.20V 時, PWM 輸出脈衝占空比為 0, 充電停止。

(3) 具體工作流程

在該電路的左邊埠接上太陽能電池板, 右邊埠接上要充電的蓄電池。當系統開始工作時, 由單片機的 A/D 模組對蓄電池的電壓進行採樣, 當採樣到的電壓低於 3.70V 時, 控制 PWM 模組輸出占空比為 100%的脈衝, 此階段為快充階段; 當電壓在 3.70V 到 4.20V 之間時, 根據電壓大小 (即蓄電池電量) 調整 PWM 輸出占空比, 此階段為慢充階段; 當電壓高於 4.20V 時, 控制 PWM 模組輸出脈衝占空比為 0, 充電停止。當 PWM 輸出的脈衝為高電平時, MOS 管導通, 三極管 Q2 的基極為 MOS 管源極輸出, 電壓較大, 因此 Q2 也導通。由於穩壓管 D2 的作用使得開關管的電壓鉗位在 -10V, 開關管導通, 太陽能電池向蓄電池充電。當脈衝處於低電平時, MOS 管及三極管 Q3 截止, 開關管斷開, 充電停止。

Figure 6 | The control circuit diagram

Chapter II System Structure

第二章 系統架構

3. Energy storage and load system

Because the solar power is very unstable, the storage device must be designed in order to improve the reliability of the power supply system. Energy storage devices stores excess energy when the system has surplus energy and when the energy is insufficient, it provides power to the load circuit.

(1) Design of energy storage system

a. System Components

The energy storage device that we concept is a lithium ion secondary battery. Its composition is as follows:

Cathode materials: the active material is lithium cobalt oxide.

Anode materials: The active material is the graphite, or something similar to the carbon of graphite structure. The thickness of conductive fluid collection is 7-15 microns of electrolytic copper foil.

Electrolyte: Dissolving lithium hexafluorophosphate of carbonic acid esters.

Diaphragm: special kind of metal composite membrane which can allow ions and electrons cross freely.

b. Working Mechanism

When charging the battery, lithium-ion generates from the positive terminal of the battery, and lithium-ion through the electrolyte movement comes to the cathode. As the carbon anode was layered structure, it has a lot of micropores for the coming lithium-ion embed into the porous carbon layer, the more embedded lithium-ion, the higher the charge capacity of the anode of lithium ion. Similarly, when the discharge of the battery (ie, we use the battery), lithium-ion embedded in the cathode carbon layer prolapse, and move back to the cathode. The more number of the lithium ion back to the cathode, the higher the discharge capacity

(2) The design of load system

a. System components

The loads system concludes mobile end-use products, electric cars, electric fans, solar street lights and other electrical equipments.

Load parameters are as follows:

Rated voltage:3.7v

Output current:170mA

Working voltage:3.7v

Limited voltage:4.2v

b. Working Mechanism

Loads refers to the consumption of electrical energy devices.It can convert electrical energy into mechanical energy, heat energy, light.When the circuit output voltage exceeds the rated voltage, the loads may be burned and Short Circuit.When the output voltage equals to the rated voltage,the loads were in its normal operation.When the output voltage is lower than the rated voltage,the loads were at low power job.

三、儲能與負載系統

由於太陽能發電及其不穩定，因此，必須設計儲能裝置以提高系統供電的可靠性。儲能裝置在能量富餘時存儲系統多餘的電能，在能量不足時向負載電路供電。

(1) 儲能系統設計

1.系統構成：

小組成員構想的儲能裝置是鋰離子二次電池，其構成如下：

正極材料：活性物質為鈷酸鋰。

負極材料：活性物質為石墨，或近似石墨結構的碳，導電集流體使用厚度 7-15 微米的電解銅箔。

電解液：溶解有六氟磷酸鋰的碳酸酯類溶劑。

隔膜：一種特殊的金屬複合膜，可以讓離子和電子自由通過。

2.作用機理：

當對電池進行充電時，電池的正極上有鋰離子生成，生成的鋰離子經過電解液運動到負極。而作為負極的碳呈層狀結構，它有很多微孔，達到負極的鋰離子就嵌入到碳層的微孔中，嵌入的鋰離子越多，充電容量越高。同樣，當對電池進行放電時（即我們使用電池的過程），嵌在負極碳層中的鋰離子脫出，又運動回正極。回正極的鋰離子越多，放電容量越高。

(2)負載系統設計

1.系統構成：

負載系統包括移動終端用電產品、電風扇、太陽能路燈等用電設備。

負載的參數如下：

額定電壓：3.7v

輸出電流：170mA

工作電壓：3.7v

限定電壓：4.2v

2.工作機理

負載指消耗電能的裝置，將電能轉換為機械能、熱能、光能等。當電路的輸出電壓超過負載的額定電壓時，負載可能被燒壞，使電路短路；當輸出電壓為負載的額定電壓時，負載正常工作；當輸出電壓低於額定電壓時，負載在低功率下工作。

Chapter III Performance show

第三章 效能展示

1. Products show

We prepare glass substrate DSSC and flexible substrates DSSC based on two different conductive substrate, as shown below

2. Instructions

a. Climatic conditions:

Ambient temperature: -20 °C to +40 °C

Operating temperature: -20 °C to +80 °C

b. Using Steps

- ① Before using the battery, please read the instruction manual and battery labels carefully;
- ② Remove the wiring and align jack, the red wire accesses to the positive(+), and the black wire accesses to the negative(-) and the other connected loads;
- ③ Put the DSSC components in light and charge to the load;
- ④ When the indicator light is red, load charging. When the light is yellow, that is to convert electrical energy into other energy stored in the storage device. When the light is green, the charging has been completed.

二、使用說明

1. 氣候條件:

環境溫度: -20°C to +40°C

工作溫度: -20°C to +80°C

2. 操作步驟

- ① 使用電池前, 請仔細閱讀使用說明書和電池表面標識;
- ② 取出數據接織, 對準介面, 將紅色導線接入正極(+), 黑色接入負極(-), 另一端連接負載;
- ③ 將 DSSC 元件置於光照下, 給負載充電;
- ④ 當指示燈為紅燈時, 表示正在為負載充電; 當指示燈為黃燈時, 表示正在將電能轉化為其他能量存儲于儲能裝置, 以備不時之需; 當指示燈為綠燈時, 表示充電已完成。

Chapter IV Characteristics

第四章 作品特色

1. Using the Bionics Principle

As the third generation solar cells, Dye-sensitized solar cells(DSSC) utilizes the process of the light reaction during photosynthesis in nature as well as the bionic principles that the butterfly wings reflect a certain band of light to design the photo-anode reflective layer of DSSC, thus it can break the barrier of the low photoelectric conversion rate.

2. Energy-saving and Ejection-decreasing

By using solar power, DSSC has many virtues as environmental -friendly, low-cost, energy-saving etc. In addition, the process of DSSC is simple, safe and pollution-free.

3. Performance characteristics

a. DSSC is flexible, which expands application range of the product.

The substrate of photo-anode can use the higher hardness of glass and use the higher softness of conductive plastics as well. Therefore, the battery can be applied to different shapes and different sizes of objects. As shown in the picture, it can be used in bending roof. In a word, the applications of DSSC are related to energy, chemicals, machinery, materials and some other industries.

b. Possess longer age, lower price than silicon solar cells.

DSSC can work in a wide temperature range and the permitted highest work temperature is 70°C. So, its service performance is more stable than CSiPV. However the service performance of CSiPV decreases as the temperature increases. At the same time, under the premise of guaranteeing the performance, the age of DSSC can up to 15-20 years.

In addition, the raw materials of the DSSC production process such as conductive glass dye and TiO₂ is cheap, the manufacture cost of DSSC is only 1/5-1/10 of CSiPV. Beside, the cost can still be reduced by about 10% when it is in the mass production.

c. Possess good transparency so that it can be used in windows and display screen.

DSSC can be made into some products which have certain degree of transparency. Thus, it can be used for making some power devices which have a requirement for transparency such as casement window (as shown on the right), roofs, automotive glass, display etc. Hence, this makes it possible that the display screen of many electronic products can realize integration.

d. DSSC can absorb weak light and can be used on the indoor lights.

DSSC not only can work well in bright light, but also can work in a certain power in weak light. Moreover, it is not sensitive for the incidence angle, so it can make full use of the refracted and reflected light. Thus it avoids the limitations of the usage of traditional silicon solar cells. As shown in the picture is the DSSC keyboard and the DSSC alarm.

e. DSSC can absorb light of a wide range of wavelength.

DSSC can absorb different wavelength range of light which depends on the dye used in the production process. DSSC has good absorption intensity in visible light. So it can make full use of solar energy which expands the age and applying fields of the products.

一、利用仿生原理

染料敏化太陽能電池作為第三代新型太陽能電池，利用自然界中綠葉光合作用的光反應過程，以及蝶翅反射一定波段光線的仿生原理，設計染料敏化太陽能電池的光陽極反射層，攻克了染料敏化太陽能電池光電轉化率低的壁壘。

二、綠色環保，節能減排

染料敏化太陽能電池利用太陽能發電，具有環保、低成本、節約能源等優點，且生產工藝流程簡單、安全、無污染。

三、作品性能特點

1.具有柔性，扩大产品应用范围

DSSC 光陽極的基底既可用硬度較大的玻璃，還可用柔軟度較高的導電塑膠，因此，電池可應用於不同形狀、不同大小的對象，如圖中所示可以用於彎曲的棚頂，其應用範圍涉及能源、化工、機械、材料等行業。

2.使用壽命長，價格較晶硅太陽能電池低

染料敏化太陽能電池的使用性能較矽太陽能電池更為穩定，可在很寬溫度範圍內工作，允許工作溫度可高達 70 度，同比之下矽電池的工作性能則隨溫度升高下降，同

時，在保證性能的前提下，其使用壽命可長達 15-20 年。

染料敏化太陽能電池生產過程中所用原材料如玻璃、染料、TiO₂ 等價格較低，製作成本僅為矽太陽能電池的 1/5-1/10，在其大規模生產之後成本仍可降低約 10%。

3.具有透明性，可用於窗戶、顯示屏

DSSC 可以製成具有一定透明度的產品，因而可以用於窗戶（如左圖所示）屋頂、汽車玻璃以及顯示器等對透明度有一要求的供電器件上，使眾多電子產品電源顯示幕一體化成為可能。

4.弱光可吸收，可在室內光源下使用

染料敏化太陽能電池不僅在強光、下能很好的工作運轉，在較弱的光線下仍能以一定的功率運轉，對光線の入射角度不敏感，可充分利用折射光和反射光，避免了傳統矽太陽能電池在使用範圍上的局限。如圖中所示的 DSSC 鍵盤和 DSSC 報警器。

5.DSSC 吸收波長範圍較硅廣

染料敏化太陽能電池可根據製作過程中使用的染料的不同來吸收不同波長範圍的光，在可見光波段具有良好的吸收強度，能夠充分利用光能，拓展了產品使用的時間和空間範圍。

Chapter V Cost and value

第五章 成本與價值

1. Functional Analysis

Dye-sensitized solar cell (Abbreviation DSSC) is produced by the annular gas-liquid interface jig magnetic separation technology which the DSSC use to improve the solar cell's performance. The DSSC's price relatively low and the fabrication process is simple. In addition, The DSSC has the potential capacity of high photoelectric conversion efficiency, It can break through the limitation of the first-generation and the second-generation solar cell's performance, and solve the problems that are existing in the silicon solar cell, such as energy consumed in large quantities, serious pollution, expensive and affect the further industrialization.

(1) The function of the main component parts

a. The photonic crystal layer

Photonic crystal layer as the absorption layer of DSSC. Its slow light effect and complicated structure lead to long optical path lengths and long dwell times before the light beam exits the layer, so the absorbed efficiency of the solar cells will be enhanced, and the photoelectric conversion efficiency will be improve.

b. The electrolyte

Select the liquid electrolyte, which has the characteristics of low saturated vapor pressure at room temperature, strongly ionic conductivity, high thermal stability, not easy burning and low toxicity and so on. The liquid electrolyte compose of Iodine Oxidation-Reduction couples, solvents, and other organic additives.

The advantages of this electrolyte are its low cost, simple fabrication process and excellent performance. It makes DSSC get better photoelectric conversion and long-term stability. More importantly, from a practical point of view, it is an environmentally friendly electrolyte which plays a role of vat dyes of positive ions and transmission charge.

c. The photoanode

Photoanode is an important component that related to the DSSC performance. It loads sensitizer and collects and transmission electrons, and the sensitization effect is the key to the photoelectric conversion efficiency of the photocell. Constructing of new nano-structured composite photoanode is of great significance to improve the efficiency of photoelectric conversion, increase the ability of electron capture, reduce the loss of electron transport between nanoparticles grain boundary barrier and electronic transmission, the suppression of photoinduced electron - hole composite.

d. The photocathode

The photocathode plays a role of collecting of the external circuit electronic and catalytic reduction I^3-/I^- . At present, Pt is still the best catalytic materials. However, because Pt is a precious metal, it's necessary to consider the impact of price factors on the cost of the battery when involving large-scale application. The one hand, people are trying to reduce the Pt usage in electrode, on the other hand, people vigorously develop the rich, low cost materials to replace Pt.

Carbon material is an ideal Pt substitutes. It is rich in resources, cheap, good thermal and chemical stability, high catalytic activity for I^3-/I^- and strongly Conductive ability. Besides, carbon is light, good conductivity, and in the aspect of DSSC's large area and flexible with important practical applications.

(2) DSSC's advantages

Omitted, refer to Chapter IV

一、功能分析

DSSC 利用提高太陽能電池性能的環形氣液介面跳汰磁分選技術生產的染料敏化太陽能電池，價格相對低廉，製作工藝簡單，擁有潛在的高光電轉換效率能力，夠突破第一、二代太陽能電池在性能上的局限，解決現有的矽光電池能耗大、污染嚴重、價格昂貴、影響進一步產業化的問題。

1. 主要組成部件的功能

(1) 光子晶體層

光子晶體層作為太陽能電池的吸收層，利用其慢光效應與在空間中複雜的結構分佈，使得光子在太陽能電池中的留滯時間與平均光子路徑增加，以達到提升太陽能電池的吸收率的效果，從而提高太陽能電池光電轉化率。

(2) 電解質

選擇液態電解質，其具有室溫下飽和蒸氣壓很低、離子電導性強、熱穩定性較高、不易燃燒和毒性低等特點，含有碘氧化還原電對、溶劑和其他有機添加劑。

該電解質的優點是成本低、製備簡單和性能優良，使 DSSC 獲得較好的光電轉化率和長期的穩定性，更重要的一點是，從實用性的角度來看，它是一種環境友好的電解質，起著還原染料正離子及傳輸電荷的作用。

(3) 光陽極

起負載敏化劑以及收集和傳輸電子作用的光陽極是關係到 DSSC 性能的重要部件，且其敏化的效果是整個光電池光電轉換效率的關鍵。構建新型納米結構複合光陽極對增加電子捕獲能力，降低納米粒子之間電子傳輸的晶界勢壘和電子傳輸的損耗，抑制光生電子-空穴的複合，提高光電轉換的效率具有重要意義。

(4) 光陰極

光陰極起著收集外電路電子和催化還原碘的作用。目前，Pt 仍然是最佳的催化材料。然而，由於 Pt 是貴金屬，大規模應用時必須要考慮價格因素對電池成本的影響。一方面人們正在努力降低 Pt 對電極的載 Pt 量，另一方面則大力發展來源豐富、價格低廉的 Pt 替代材料。

碳材料資源豐富，價格便宜，熱穩定性和化學穩定性好，對碘催化活性高，導電能力強，是一種理想的 Pt 替代物，並且碳對電極質輕、導電性好，在 DSSC 的大面積化和柔性化方面具有重要的實際應用價值。

2. DSSC 的優勢

略，見第四章

Chapter V Cost and Value

第五章 成本與價值

2. Cost Analysis

Choosing different materials that make up of DSSC, the cost is also different. The better performance of the materials, the more expensive the price is, resulting in the high cost. So it can be optimized by selecting, making a minimum of DSSC production costs and the optimal performance to achieve its maximum value.

Firstly, analyzing the DSSC main structure to form part of the cost-consuming:

Table 1 | Cost analysis of structure

Raw material	Cost(¥)	原料	成本
Polystyrene	500/bottle	聚苯乙烯 (PS)	500 元/瓶
Electrolyte	500/ bottle	電解質	500/瓶
N719 Dye	450/ bottle	N719 染料	450/瓶
FTO Conductive Glass	30/piece	FTO 導電玻璃	30 元/片
TiO ₂ Pastes	5/g	TiO ₂ 漿料	5 元/g
Carbon	1/g	碳(C)	1 元/g

Secondly, analyzing each block of the DSSC's cost, specification: 10cm * 7.5cm.

二、成本分析

製作 DSSC 的各組成部分可選的材料不同，其成本也不同，選用性能越好的材料，其價格越昂貴，造成成本過高，所以可以通過優化選擇，使得 DSSC 的生產成本最小，性能最優，實現其最大價值。

首先，分析 DSSC 主要的結構組成部分所耗費的成本：

其次，每塊 DSSC 的成本分析，規格：10cm*7.5cm。

Table 2 | Cost analysis of each cell

DSSC Component	Raw Materials	Cost(¥)	DSSC 部件	原料	成本(元)
photonic crystal layer	Polystyrene	3.5	光子晶體	聚苯乙烯 (PS)	3.5
Electrolyte	Liquid Electrolyte	3.5	電解質	液態電解質	3.5
photoanode	TiO ₂ Pastes	0.1	光陽極	TiO ₂ 漿料	0.1
	N719 Dye	1.0		N719 染料	1.0
	FTO Conductive Glass	0.5		FTO 導電玻璃	0.5
photocathode	Carbon	0.02	光陰極	碳(C)	0.02
	FTO Conductive Glass	0.5		FTO 導電玻璃	0.5
Total		9.12	總計		9.12

Therefore, the production of a size 10cm * 7.5cm of the DSSC cost ¥608;

A specification is 10cm * 7.5cm DSSC total capacity of approximately 1W,

So the unit production cost is ¥10/W

因此，得出生產一塊規格為 10cm*7.5cm 的 DSSC 的成本為 9.12元；

而一塊規格為 10cm*7.5cm 的 DSSC 的總產能約為 1W，

所以單位產能的成本為 9.12元/W

Chapter V Cost and value

第五章 成本與價值

3. Value Analysis

With the proposal of the energy saving and emission reduction, and in order to make the photovoltaic industry gain greater economic benefits as well as users get greater value in use, so analyzing DSSC's value to achieve DSSC performance optimization, cost reduction and improve its value to maximization.

According to the theory of value analysis, Increase the value of DSSC by analyzing DSSC's function and cost. So there are two directions to improve the DSSC's value: First, to improve the function of DSSC, the second is to reduce the cost of the DSSC.

Increase value of DSSC mainly in its parts to functional optimization and cost reduction, specifically for the following aspects:

(1) Reducing the cost

-- Economies of scale will make DSSC cost has dropped significantly

Relatively low cost and large-scale production can contribute to the DSSC cost dropped significantly, the following table for the DSSC cost of expanding production decline:

Table 3 | The cost analysis of DSSC in mass production

Materials	Cost of 2MW Capacity (¥/M)	Cost of 20MW Capacity (¥/M)	原料	2MW 成本(元/瓦)	20MW 成本(元/瓦)
Polystyrene	25	12	聚苯乙烯 (PS)	25	12
Electrolyte	25	12	電解質	25	12
N719 Dye	4.5	2	N719 染料	4.5	2
FTO	3	1	FTO 導電玻璃	3	1
TiO ₂ Pastes	0.2	0.01	TiO ₂ 漿料	0.2	0.01
Carbon	0.1	0.005	碳(C)	0.1	0.005
Total	57.8	27.015	總成本	57.8	27.015

(2) Function optimization

- Synthesis of new dye molecules
- High-quality photonic crystals
- Selection and optimization of the electrolyte
- Optimization design of the photocathode structure
- Photoanode materials selection and optimization
- Improvement of DSSC preparation process

(3) Social and environmental benefits

Solar power is a kind of clean renewable energy with rich resource, it has unique advantages and huge potential for development, and it is significance to make full use of solar energy to energy save and environmental protection. Research and development of flexible DSSC can provide an effective way to alleviate the environmental pollution and energy shortage problems faced by the sustainable development of human.

First of all, of DSSC solar power generation in favor of saving non-renewable resources, balance the energy of single-supply situation; secondly, it can reduce greenhouse gas emissions (including CO, NO, etc.) to achieve the clean use of energy can be made to protect the environment, save energy contribution.

三、價值分析

隨著國家節能減排的提出，同時為了使光伏行業獲得更大的經濟效益，使用戶得到更大的使用價值，對 DSSC 進行價值分析，實現 DSSC 在性能優化、成本降低的前提下最大化地提高其價值。

根據價值分析理論，通過對 DSSC 的功能及成本的分析，提高 DSSC 的價值，所以提高 DSSC 價值的的方向主要有兩個：一是提高 DSSC 的功能，二是降低 DSSC 的成本。

提高 DSSC 價值主要集中在對其部件進行功能的優化和成本的降低，具體為以下幾個方面：

1. 成本降低

——規模效應會使 DSSC 成本大幅下降

相對成本較低，且大規模的產量可以促進 DSSC 成本的大幅下降，下表為 DSSC 在產量擴大之後成本的下降情況：

2. 功能優化

- 新型染料分子的合成
- 高品質光子晶體的製備
- 電解質的選擇和優化
- 陰極結構的優化設計
- 光陽極材料的選擇及優化
- 改進 DSSC 製備工藝

3. 社會效益和環境效益

太陽能是一種資源豐富的清潔可再生能源，具有獨特的優勢和巨大的開發潛力，充分利用太陽能對節省能源、保護環境有重要的意義。柔性 DSSC 的研製和開發，可以為緩解人類可持續發展所面臨的環境污染和能源短缺等難題提供了一條行之有效的途徑。

首先，DSSC 利用太陽發電有利於節省不可再生資源，平衡能源的單一供給情況；其次，可以實現減排溫室氣體(包括 CO、NO 等)、實現能源的清潔利用，可對保護環境、節省能源作出貢獻。

Chapter VI Combination with Industry

第六章 產業結合

1. Technology Transfer

As mentioned in the catalog of guidance of adjustment of industrial structure which is published in 2011, the key technology, equipment and products which play an important role in promoting the economic and social development and are helpful for resource conservation, protecting environment, optimizing and upgrading of industrial structure, what's more, which need the encourage and support by policy, should be encouraged. This provides a hard-won opportunity for the transfer of the technology for DSSC production.

First of all, from the point of view of demand, with the development of technology and the transformation of people's notion for life, solar products with its environment-friendly and energy saving characteristics more and more popular. The researches for DSSC provide the development of solar energy production which is towards diversification and individuation with Technical support. This background will bring vast development space to the technology transfer to business.

Secondly, from the point of view of technology, the use of technology for DSSC production in solar enterprise is actually a combination of technology and productive process. It takes effect only by combination of technology and productive process, not with technology research alone. In the process of production we can make innovation and progress in technology, and then complete the optimization for production process and the production itself through the process of technology.

Thirdly, from the point of view of industry, with the help and guidance from industry association, we should set up an Industry-University-Research Institute Alliance with backbone enterprise, make it easier for the enterprise to acquire advanced technology and reduce their cost. In this way the whole industry will conduct the development, transfer and application of technology massively and jointly, and then it will promote the technology of this field in the whole industry, achieving social and economic benefits.

2. Application in Industry

① We can make the base of DSSC by hard glass or soft conductive plastic, therefore, the appearance of DSSC gains plasticity and it can be made into various solar products.

② The base of DSSC is usually transparent, so DSSC can be made into production which are power supply device needing transparency, such as windows, roof, glass, displayer and so on. This makes the integration of power and display be possible.

③ DSSC absorbs and transforms light energy by chemical dyestuff. different dyes can absorb light of different bands, so DSSC can absorb light well which is visible to us, and make full use of light energy.

④ DSSC is not sensitive to the incident angle of light, so it can make full use of light from refraction and reflection. It can do a good job in the bright light like sunlight, while in the weak light like indoor incandescent lamp it can also keep working at a certain power. So, DSSC can be made into solar products which can be used indoor, such as DSSC keyboard, DSSC alarm etc.

一、技術轉移

2011年公佈的《產業結構調整指導目錄》提出，“對經濟社會發展有重要促進作用，有利於節約資源、保護環境、產業結構優化升級，需要採取政策措施予以鼓勵和支持的關鍵技術、裝備及產品”予以鼓勵。這一政策為 DSSC 製作技術的轉移提供了難得的機遇。

一是從需求的角度，隨著科技的發展和人們生活觀念的轉變，太陽能產品以其環保、節能的特性越來越受到市場的青睞。對染料敏化太陽能電池的研究為太陽能產品多元化和個性化發展提供了技術上的支撐。這樣的需求背景為 DSSC 製作技術向企業轉移提供了很大空間。

二是從技術的角度，DSSC 製作技術在太陽能企業的應用實際上是一種技術、工藝的集成，僅對其本身的技術研究是不夠的，它需要太陽能電池加工過程中的技術工藝知識、技巧，兩者的有效結合才能有所成效。在生產的過程中，實現技術的創新和進步，再利用技術的改進完成生產工藝流程及產品的優化。

三是從行業的角度，在行業協會的幫助和指導下，與行業骨幹企業結成產學研聯盟，降低企業獲得先進共性技術的進入門檻和使用成本，形成面向行業的規模化共性技術開發、轉移和應用，從而提升整個行業在該領域的技術水準，並取得社會和經濟效益。

二、工業應用

1. 染料敏化太陽能電池光陽極的基底既可用硬度較大的玻璃，還可用柔軟度較高的導電塑料，因此，在外型上的可塑性很強，可製成各種形狀、大小的太陽能產品。

2. 染料敏化太陽能電池的基底透明，可以製成具有一定透明度的產品，因而可以用於窗戶、屋頂、汽車玻璃以及顯示器等對透明度有一定要求的供電器件上，使眾多電子產品電源顯示幕一體化成為可能。

3. 染料敏化太陽能電池利用化學染料吸收、轉化光能，使用不同的染料即可吸收不同波段的光，在可見光波段具有良好的吸收能力，能夠充分利用光能。

4. 染料敏化太陽能電池對光線的入射角度不敏感，可充分利用折射光和反射光，不僅在強光如太陽光下能很好的工作運轉，在較弱的光線如室內白熾燈、日光燈等光源下仍能以一定的功率運轉。可生產在室內使用的太陽能產品，染料敏化太陽能電池鍵盤和染料敏化太陽能電池報警器等。

Chapter VI Combination with Industry

第六章 產業結合

3. Production line

We will combine innovative production concept and advanced production technology to set up a production line which including the preparation of all parts of batteries, the assembly of the batteries, performance testing of the batteries and quality testing of the batteries. In this process, strict quality control and battery sub-file are needed in order to obtain the high performance of dye-sensitized solar cells.

The following picture shows the distribution of DSSC production line and process control procedures.

三、生產線

我們將結合創新的生產理念及先進的生產技術，組建一條集電池各部件的制作、電池的組裝以及電池性能測試、品質測試的高效生產線，在此過程中嚴格進行質量監控與電池分檔，以期獲得性能優異的染料敏化太陽能電池。

下图为 DSSC 生產線分布及工藝控制步驟圖：

Figure 7 | Production line

Note:

- ① QC(Quality Control): Defects and damage detection, the exclusion of bad film, Verification process;
- ② PC(Process Control):Testing process parameters, Cell efficiency, marked level, Control the process;
- ③ CT(Classification Tools): Qualitative cell quality, classified products (Raw Material and End Product),Classification Tools.

注：

- ①品質控制：包括缺陷和損傷檢測、壞片的剔除、核對工藝；
- ②工藝控制：包括測試工藝參數、電池效率、標明級別、控制工藝；
- ③分檔：包括定性電池品質、分類產品（原料與成品）、分檔。

Chapter VII Perspective Vista

第七章 遠景展望

1. The Battery Parts

According to the parts of DSSC, we mainly concentrated on the following areas:

(1) The synthesis of new dye molecules

We are committed to the preparation of new dye molecules which are able to increase ability to absorb long-wave and has a high optical cross-section and the ability to absorb near infrared.

(2) The preparation of high-quality photonic crystals

The photonic crystals of butterfly wings structure have the uniform particle size, so the reflected light wavelength band is limited. If total band-gap light reflection is wanted, we need to prepare the photonic crystals of Anti-opal structure, or the photonic crystal combined a diverse different particle size. All these methods can reach the effect of total band-gap light reflection.

(3) The selection and optimization of the electrolyte

Because the solid DSSC sensitizer has redox potential so that it can match better with the work function of the vacancy. As a result, solid electrolyte instead of liquid electrolyte can enhance and improve the long-term stability of the battery when used in DSSC.

(4) The optimization design of the cathode structure

The preparation of cathode uses conductive glass as its basement, and it use different methods to be coated with graphite, platinum or conductive polymers. At present, the better method is the platinum-plated, but its cost is too high, so we are committed to the development of conductive polymers which have excellent performance and low cost.

(5) The selection and optimization of the photo-anode materials

Overburden sensitizer and the photo-anode which has the ability to collect and transmit electron are the important components related to the DSSC performance. Building new complex photo-anode of nanostructure can increase the ability to capture the electron, reduce the grain boundary barrier of electron transport between nano-particles and the loss of electronic transmission, inhibit the compound of photo electron – hole. This is the key to improve the photoelectric conversion rate. ZnO has higher electron transfer rate, TiO₂ has higher electron injection efficiency. Therefore, doping TiO₂ on the coat of ZnO and then the photo-anode of ZnO/TiO₂ nanostructure combining photonic crystals applied in DSSC will make the DSSC which has excellent properties.

2. The Technology

Improving the preparation process of photonic crystal, optimizing the sorting device, and then filtering out the more excellent performance of the PS ball, with these steps, the excellent photonic crystal can be used in DSSC. Improving some parameter settings, exploring the methods of preparation of nano-TiO₂ porous film, and then choosing the best ways, with these steps, the various components of DSSC can be made of.

一、電池部件

對染料敏化太陽能電池部件的研究我們主要集中在以下幾個方面：

1. 新型染料分子的合成

致力於製備能使吸收長波能力增加並且具有很高光學橫斷面和吸收近紅外光能力的新型染料分子；

2. 高品質光子晶體的製備

蝶翅結構光子晶體由於其粒徑均一，因此反射光波長是有限波段的，想實現全帶隙的光反射，我們需要製備出 Anti-opal 結構的光子晶體，或製備出多元不同粒徑組合的光子晶體，均能達到全帶隙反射的效果；

3. 電解質的選擇和優化

由於固態染料敏化太陽能電池敏化劑的氧化還原電位，可以和空位導體的工作函數更好的匹配，因此以固態電解質取代液態電解質液應用於 DSSC 中來提高和改善電池的長期穩定性；

4. 陰極結構的優化設計

陰極的製備以導電玻璃片為基底，採用不同方法鍍上石墨、鉑或導電聚合物。目前，屬鍍鉑的效果較好，但由於鍍鉑成本太高，因此我們致力於開發性能優良價格低廉的導電聚合物取而代之；

5. 光陽極材料的選擇及優化

起負載敏化劑以及收集和傳輸電子作用的光陽極是關係到 DSSC 性能的重要部件，構建新型納米結構複合光陽極對增加電子捕獲能力，降低納米粒子之間電子傳輸的晶界勢壘和電子傳輸的損耗，抑制光生電子-空穴的複合，是提高光電轉化率的關鍵，而 ZnO 具有較高的電子傳輸速率，TiO₂ 具有較高的電子注入效率，因此利用 TiO₂ 對 ZnO 進行包覆，製備 ZnO/TiO₂ 納米結構複合光陽極，結合光子晶體在染料敏化太陽能電池的應用，以期製備出性能優異的 DSSC。

二、工藝技術

改進光子晶體製備工藝，優化分選裝置，篩選出性能更加優異的 PS 小球進而製備出優異的光子晶體應用於 DSSC 中；改進一些參數設置，探索製備納米 TiO₂ 多孔薄膜的方法，選擇最優方案製備 DSSC 各部件。

3. Environmental Protections

Dedicated to the study of the third generation of solar cells and applying the photonic crystals of butterfly wings structure to DSSC greatly improves the efficiency of the battery and promotes the industrialization of the DSSC, and also makes a tremendous contribution to save energy and decrease ejection.

4. The Expectations on TECO creativity contest

(1) Improving competition mechanisms

TECO Technology Creativity Contest advocates the importance of the research of the "Green Tech" and encourages the spirit of the young innovative research, in turn, it can develop the required personnel for green energy and contribute to the enhancement of the "Green Tech" research and technology, so that it will have high reputation and influence both in and out. If it can improve competition mechanisms, we think it can achieve better development. Such as establishing more competition arenas in mainland China, adopting the layers of the selection mechanism, expanding the game coverage area and so on, in order to improve competitiveness and achieve more and more outstanding works and ideas.

(2) Establishing the information platform of science and technology

The establishment of the information platform can make exchange channels for government, businesses, schools and scholars. The scope of the platform can be extended to the international scope, while having a more far-reaching influence on combining production, learning and research, so that the information platform will be a bridge of communication and exchange for people to promote energy-saving and ejection-decreasing.

(3) Enhancing the technology and cultural exchange between the people across the Taiwan Straits

We suggest that it could organize scientific research and exchange, enhance the technology and cultural exchange and cooperation between the people across the Taiwan Straits, and build the image of Chinese technological and cultural. Moreover, it can hold the science and technology exhibition in cooperation with the China Association for Science and Technology in order to establish a new pipeline for cross-strait academic and to deepen further exchange and cooperation between the people across the Taiwan Straits.

三、環境保護

致力於第三代太陽能電池的研究，並將仿生蝶翅光子晶體用於 DSSC 中，大大提高了電池的效率，推進染料敏化太陽能電池的產業化，為節約能源、減排環保做出巨大的貢獻。

四、對東元科技創意競賽的期望

1. 完善比賽機制

東元科技創意競賽宣導對於「Green Tech」研發的重視，並鼓勵青年創新研究的精神，進而為綠色能源之發展儲備所需之人才，促成「Green Tech」研究發展技術的提升，在國內外享有較高的聲譽和影響力，如能改進比賽機制，可取得更好的發展。如在中國大陸成立多個賽區，採用層層選拔機制，擴大比賽覆蓋區域，以提高競爭性，獲得更多、更優秀的作品和創意。

2. 建立科技創意資訊平臺

資訊平臺的建立，可以為政府、企業、學校和學者提供交流的管道，平臺的範圍可以延伸至國際範圍上，同時為產學研的結合提供更深遠的作用，使科技創意資訊平臺成為促進對節能減排關注者溝通和交流的橋樑。

3. 加強兩岸科技文化交流

舉辦科研交流會，加強兩岸科技文化交流合作，共同塑造中華科技文化時代形象；與中國科協合作舉辦科技作品展覽，為兩岸學術界建立起聯繫的新管道，從而深化兩岸科技的更進一步交流與合作。

Chapter VIII Appendix

第八章 附錄

1. Source code

```
#include<p24fj64ga006.h>
#define uchar unsigned char
#define uint unsigned int
uchar RESERED[100];
uint get=0;

//A/D 初始化函數
void AD_init()
{
    AD1PCFG=0;          //設置 A/D 埠, PORTB 埠的 16 路輸入全為模
擬輸入
    AD1CON2=0X6000;     //設置 A/D 參考電壓, 緩衝器填充模式, 每次
採樣後中斷, 輸入不掃描
    AD1CON3=0X0200;     //設置 A/D 轉換時鐘 Tcy/2
    AD1CON1=0X00E0;     //採樣時鐘, 轉換觸發模式, 資料輸出格式,
自動轉換
                        //手動啟動採樣, 空間模式繼續採樣
    AD1CHS=0X0002;     //設置輸入通道, 通道 0 正輸入為 AN2, 負輸
入為 Vr(AVss)
    AD1CSSL=0;         //輸入不掃描
    AD1CON1bits.ADON=1; //打開 A/D
    AD1CON1bits.SAMP=1; //啟動採樣
    while(!AD1CON1bits.DONE);//等待轉換結束
    get=ADC1BUF0;
}

//PWM 初始化
void PWM_init()        //簡單脈寬調製初始化
{
    OC1CON=0x0000;
    OC1R=15625;
    OC1RS=15625;
    OC1CON=0x000E;     //T3 作為時基
}

//計時器 3 初始化
void T3_init()
{
    T3CON=0x0020;      //分頻比為 1:64
    TMR3=0x0000;
    PR3=31250-1;       //500ms
    IPC2bits.T3IP=5;
    IFS0bits.T3IF=0;
    IEC0bits.T3IE=1;
    T3CONbits.TON=1;
}
```

一、原始碼

```
//計時器 3 中斷服務函數
void __attribute__((__interrupt__, auto_psv))
_T3Interrupt (void)
{
    if(get<760)        //當電壓低於 3.7V 時
快充
                        OC1RS=31260;
                        else if(get<780)
                            OC1RS=25000;
                            else if(get<800)
                                OC1RS=20000; //電壓介於
3.7V~4.2V 之間時根據電壓大小改變充電速度
                                else if(get<820)
                                    OC1RS=15000;
                                    else if(get<840)
                                        OC1RS=10000;
                                        else if(get<860)
                                            OC1RS=5000;
                                            else
                                                OC1RS=0; //當電壓高於 4.2V 時停止充電
IFS0bits.T3IF=0;
}

//主函數
int main()
{
    PWM_init();
    T3_init();
    AD_init();
    while(1)
    {
        AD1CON1bits.SAMP=1;
        while(!AD1CON1bits.DONE);
        get=ADC1BUF0;
    }
}
```

2. Patent documents

Qualified in first instance (NO.201110355808.8)

中华人民共和国国家知识产权局

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发文日:

2012年01月04日

申请号或专利号: 201110355808.8

发文序号: 2011122900875300

申请人或专利权人: XXXXXXXXXX

发明创造名称: 可连续作业的气液界面跳汰磁分选可控环形装置

发明专利申请初步审查合格通知书

1. 上述专利申请, 经初步审查, 符合专利法实施细则第 44 条的规定。
2. 申请人于 2011 年 11 月 10 日提出提前公布声明, 经审查, 符合专利法实施细则第 46 条的规定, 专利申请进入公布准备程序。
3. 申请人于 2011 年 11 月 10 日提出实质审查请求, 经审查, 符合专利法第 35 条及其实施细则第 93 条的规定, 专利申请在公布之后将进入实质审查程序。
4. 初步审查合格的上述发明专利申请是以:
 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的说明书摘要;
 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的摘要附图;
 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的权利要求书;
 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的说明书;
 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的说明书附图
 为基础的。

审查员: 刘时娇

审查部门: 初审及流程管理部

The substantive examination (NO.201110355808.8)

中华人民共和国国家知识产权局

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张雪梅

发文日:

2012年05月23日

申请号或专利号: 201110355808.8

发文序号: 2012051400096060

申请人或专利权人: [REDACTED]

发明创造名称: 可连续作业的气液界面跳汰磁分选可控环形装置

发明专利申请公布及进入实质审查阶段通知书

上述专利申请, 经初步审查, 符合专利法实施细则第44条的规定。根据专利法第34条的规定, 该申请在28卷19号专利公报上予以公布。

根据申请人提出的实质审查请求, 经审查, 符合专利法第35条及实施细则第96条的规定, 该专利申请进入实质审查阶段。

注: 附发明专利申请单行本一份。

提示:

1. 根据专利法实施细则第51条第1款的规定, 发明专利申请人自收到本通知书之日起3个月内, 可以对发明专利申请主动提出修改。

2. 专利电子申请不提供专利申请单行本, 申请人可以访问国家知识产权局政府网站 (www.sipo.gov.cn), 在专利检索栏目中查询公布文本。

3. 申请文件修改格式要求:

对权利要求修改的应当提交相应的权利要求替换项, 涉及权利要求引用关系时, 则需要将相应权项一起替换补正。如果申请人需要删除部分权项, 申请人应该提交整理后连续编号的部分权利要求书。

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审查员: 李园夏

审查部门: 专利局初审及流程管理部

联系电话: 62356655

210308
2010.2

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张雪梅

发文日:

2012 年 01 月 04 日

申请号或专利号: 201110355807.3

发文序号: 2011122900875320

申请人或专利权人: XXXXXXXXXX

发明创造名称: 环形气液界面跳汰磁分选装置

发明专利申请初步审查合格通知书

1. 上述专利申请, 经初步审查, 符合专利法实施细则第 44 条的规定。
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 - 2011 年 11 月 10 日提交的说明书附图
 为基础的。

审查员: 刘时娇

审查部门: 初审及流程管理部

210304
2010. 4

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The substantive examination (NO.201110355807.3)

中华人民共和国国家知识产权局

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申请人或专利权人:

发明创造名称: 环形气液界面跳汰磁分选装置

发明专利申请公布及进入实质审查阶段通知书

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审查部门: 专利局初审及流程管理部

联系电话: 62356655

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3. References

- [1] O'Regan B, Gratzel M. A low-cost, high-efficiency solar cell based on dye-sensitized colloidal TiO₂ films[J]. *Lett Nature*, 1991, 353:737.
- [2] Bach U, Lupo D, Comte P, et al. Solid-state dye-sensitized mesoporous TiO₂ solar cells with high photon-to-electron conversion efficiencies [J]. *Lett Nature*, 1998, 395:583.
- [3] Nazeeruddin M K, Pechy P, Renouard T, et al [J]. *J Am Chem Soc*, 2001, 123:1613.
- [4] Gratzel M. [J]. *J Photochem and Photobiol A Chem*, 2004, 164:1.
- [5] Wang P, Shaik M, Zakeeruddin S M. [J]. *Adv Mater*, 2004, 16:1806.
- [6] Arakawa H, Hara H, et al. [J]. *J Chem Soc, Dalton Trans*, 2000, 2817.
- [7] Dai Songyuan, Wang Kongjia, Weng Jian, et al. Internal Series Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Module and Assembly Method: China, 200410014455.5[P]. 2005-09-28
- [8] Lucio Di Jasio. 16-bit microcontroller C programming language [M]. Italy
- [9] Xie Jiakui. Electronic circuit [M]. Higher Education Press. Beijing
- [10] Marian Florescu, Hwang Lee, Irina Puscasu, Martin Pralle Lucia Florescu [J]. *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells* 91 (2007) 1599–1610
- [11] N.P. Harder, P. Wu. *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* 18 (2003) S151.
- [12] Zhijian Zhang, Deqing Yu, Yulin Zhang, Kaifang Xu. Analysis of Energy for Solar Cell and Technological Development of Thin-Film Battery [J]. *Yunnan Metallurgy*. 2008, 37
- [13] M. Florescu, S. Scheel, H. Haffner, H. Lee, D. Strelakov, P.L. Knight, J.P. Dowling, *Europhys. Lett.* 69 (6) (2005) 945.
- [14] Jianjun Wang, Jinxia Liu. The Investigation and Development of Solar Cell and Materials [J]. *Journal of Zhejiang Wanli University*, 2006, 19(5).
- [15] Tianhang Zheng. Analysis of Energy Consumption, Investment Economy and Social benefits of Photovoltaic Industry [J]. *Shanghai Electric Power*, 2006(4).
- [16] Yuanqing Li. The Cost and Market Analysis of Light-gathering Solar Battery [J]. *Value Engineering*, 2010, 29(20).
- [17] Guiqiang Wang, Zhongjun Fu. Dye-Sensitized Nano-crystalline TiO₂ Solar Cells [J]. *Dyestuffs and Coloration*, 2005, 42(5).
- [18] Zhexun Yu, Dongmei Li, Da Qin, Hui cheng Sun, Yiduo Zhang, Yanhong Luo, Qingbo Meng. Research and Development of Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells [J]. *Materials China*, 2009, 28(7-8).
- [19] Zhen Zhang, Hui Shen, Ruixian Cai, Yong Liu. Progress Trend and Cost Analysis of On-grid Photovoltaic System [J]. *Power Technology*, 2008, 32(10).
- [20] Chao Zeng, Xuedong Lu, Jiagang Sun. Valuable Analysis on "T" Type Graphite Products [J]. *Charcoal*, 2000(1).

基於仿生蝶翅 PC 結構改進的染料敏化太陽能電池
Improved DSSC Based on the PC Structure of Biomimetic Butterfly Wings

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